

Flagship Project

Anticancer activity of bee venom (*Apis mellifera anatoliaca*)

Ayse Nalbantsoy

(Reference Person)

Leadership & team

Steering committee:

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Current Project Members: Maria P. Ikonopoulou (COST action MC member), Yiannis Sarigiannis (COST action MC member), Ekin Varol (COST action WG1&2 member), H. Mehmet Kayılı, Banu Yücel, Ayse Nalbantsoy (COST MC action member)

Involvement of Participants:

Field study: Collection of bee venom from the field, selection of bee venom, freeze-drying and sharing with teams: Ekin Varol, Banu Yücel, Ayse Nalbantsoy

Testing on different cell lines and potential mechanisms of action study: Maria P. Ikonopoulou,

Proteomic studies, determination of melittin sequence: H. Mehmet Kayılı

Synthesis of melittin: Yiannis Sarigiannis

Summary

Bee venom has traditionally been used for various medical applications. Specifically, melittin is an important invaluable medium-length peptide present in bee venom that displays great pharmaceutical potential and presents several structural differences depending on the genus and flora. Türkiye has a rich diversity of honeybee species, which could pioneer the development of melittin-derived drug candidate peptides with pharmaceutical potential including against cancer. In this study, bee venoms were collected from the apiary located entirely in an eucalyptus forest. Crude bee venoms containing melittin were tested on healthy human neonatal foreskin fibroblast (NFF) and human melanoma (SK-MEL-103 and MM96L) cells by MTT assay for cytotoxicity. Additionally, MM96L cells were stained with oil red and imaged with a fluorescence microscope to investigate lipid accumulation. To determine the chromatographic profile and purify melittin, 1 mg of soluble venom was injected into an RP-HPLC, Shimadzu (Tokio, Japan), using a C18 column (4.6 × 250 mm, 5 µm particle size) equipped with a photodiode array detector. The elution process occurred at a flow rate of 1 ml/min, and detection was performed at 230 nm. A linear gradient from solution A (0.12% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) in water) to 60% solution B (0.10% TFA in acetonitrile) was applied over 60 minutes. Subfractions were manually collected, one by one, and then dried under vacuum for further analysis. The results showed that crude bee venom has significantly higher cytotoxicity on melanoma cells than healthy cells at a concentration of 5 µg/mL and increased lipid accumulation at a concentration of 3 µg/mL. Based on the results, the primary structure of the venom melittin was determined by proteomic analysis and reproduced in silico. Future experiments will confirm whether melittin was responsible for the observed cytotoxicity in melanoma cell lines as well as its underlying molecular mechanism.

Outputs: Evaluation of anticancer activity of selected crude bee venom and synthesized melittin, implying (we have not evaluated lipid evaluation due to melittin. We only checked the crude venoms) lipidotxic potential in melanoma cells.

Budget: Provided by participants

Action tools: Presentation at the training school on bee venom collection techniques (Ayse Nalbantsoy in Venom extractions: manual vs electric stimulations vs venom gland dissection, why does it matter?, 5th-7th of July 2023, Pole Chimie Balard Recherche, IBMM, Montpellier, France) and STSM participation (Oznur Su Yentur, WG2 member (in the Laboratory of Maria P. Ikonopoulou.) Poster presentation at 2nd International Congress, European Venom Network, Darwin-Dohrn Museum - Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn, 23-25 September 2024.

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